

THE IMPORTANCE OF PHONOLOGY AND THE KNOWLEDGE OF
PHONETICS. IN TEACHING AND LEARNING

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Annotation: In this article I want to clarify how the teaching of pronunciation has witnessed remarkable changes throughout the history of language teaching and learning. Some practical techniques and activities, which involve the use of phonetics and phonology in the teaching of pronunciation, will be presented.

Key words: Phonology, phonetics. Scavenger hunt, syllable, stress.

The present article endeavours to highlight the importance of phonetics and phonology. Phonology is the study of the sound system of a language. It is important to language learners because it can help them to understand how the sounds of a language are made, how they are used, and how they are related to each other. By understanding phonology, language learners can improve their pronunciation, and they can also learn to distinguish between different sounds in a language. Language is made up of sounds, and words must have sounds. Phonology is a component of language comprehension that is by nature also a component of understanding. The Simple View of Reading, on the other hand, clearly emphasizes reading. It's up to someone who generalizes it to correct any misunderstandings or misapplications. It is critical to be able to hear and speak phonemes (phonemic awareness) in order to read and write. According to new research, phonemic awareness instruction appears to be the most important factor influencing reading outcomes. Some argue that this should be the primary focus of

systematic phonics instruction. It is also important to teach phonology in language teaching because it can assist students in understanding language structure and recognizing and analyzing sound patterns. Students can also gain a better understanding of what words and sentences mean by practicing phonology. In teaching phonology, language teachers gain an understanding of how a language sounds and is used in sentences, which is critical for understanding the sounds. Knowing a language's phonology can help teachers avoid mispronunciation and articulation. The importance of teaching pronunciation in English language is obvious. It is generally recognized that pronunciation is the first and most important thing in communication. When mispronounced, the simplest words will prevent the speaker from communicating effectively in English, so pronunciation can be considered as the main troublemakers from the view of language intelligibility. Effective pronunciation teaching offers learners a choice in how to express themselves and feel a pleasure in exchanging ideas. Pronunciation is more important than it seems to be and has always been acknowledged that it is a fundamental part of learner's oral ability in the target language. Intensive contact with good pronunciation models in the beginning of the learning process. Help to find out effective way of teaching English pronunciation especially tailor-made for learners/teachers to cultivate spoken English that is easy to understand for listeners, develop strategies for spoken language that serves communicative needs effectively an increase self-confidence in teaching with useful methodology based on research, meeting the needs of teachers.

Here are some activities in teaching phonology:

Identify Sounds and their sources

The Sound Around Box is a versatile classroom tool that will help you teach early language and literacy concepts in a fun and hands-on way. It provides the opportunity for many group activities which will help children develop important

social skills as they engage in multisensory play with rhymes, syllables, beginning sounds, alphabet knowledge, letters, word parts, and test their memory skills!

Road trip rhymes

While you're out driving in the car, spot something out the window and ask your child, "what rhymes with tree or car or shop?" Then switch roles and have your child spot something and ask you for a rhyme. This can turn into a game of nonsense rhymes ("What rhymes with tree stump?") but that's great for practicing sounds, too!

"I spy" first sounds

Practice beginning sounds with this simple "I spy" game at home, on a walk, or at the grocery store. Choose words with distinctive, easy-to-hear beginning sounds. For example, if you're in the bathroom you can say, "I spy something red that starts with the "s" ssss sound (soap)."

Sound scavenger hunt

Choose a letter sound, then have your child find things around your house that start with the same sound. "Can you find something in our house that starts with the letter "p" pppppp sound? Picture, pencil, pear"

Used literatures:

1. Kambaraliyeva, I. (2024, April). BREAKING LANGUAGE BARRIERS: HOW LANGUAGE LEARNING PROMOTES GLOBAL UNDERSTANDING. In *Conference Proceedings: Fostering Your Research Spirit* (pp. 615-617).
2. Aripovna, R. S. (2024). THE COGNITIVE WAYS TO LEAD AN ADVANCED LEARNER TO MAKE SELF-ASSESSMENT: Yangi O'zbekiston taraqqiyotida tadqiqotlarni o'rni va rivojlanish omillari. *Yangi*

- O'zbekiston taraqqiyotida tadqiqotlarni o'rni va rivojlanish omillari*, 7(3), 116-121.
3. Bazarova, D. (2022). Variability of phraseological units. *Science and innovation*, 1(B7), 483.
 4. Bazarova, D. (2024). TA'LIM RUS TILIDA OLIB BORILADIGAN GURUHLARDA "O 'ZBEK TILIDA SO 'Z TARKIBI" MAVZUSINI O 'RGATISH TAJRIBASIDAN. *O 'ZBEK TILINING XORIJDA O 'QITILISHI: TA 'LIM NAZARIYASI VA AMALIYOTI*, 1(01), 88-90.
 5. Aliqulova, M. (2024). АНАЛИЗ ИЗУЧЕНИЯ ЯЗЫКА И СТИЛЯ ПРОИЗВЕДЕНИЙ АИ КУПРИНА. *O 'ZBEK TILINING XORIJDA O 'QITILISHI: TA 'LIM NAZARIYASI VA AMALIYOTI*, 1(01), 82-87.
 6. Аликулова, М. (2023). ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ЭПИТЕТОВ В ПРОИЗВЕДЕНИЯХ АИ КУПРИНА. *Scientific progress*, 4(5), 387-390.
 7. Khasanova, S., Akisheva, N., & Zholayeva, M. (2023). Methodological aspects of tax planning in the context of sustainable development. *Revista Gestão & Tecnologia*, 23(3), 286-298.
 8. Sarsebaevich, A. M., & Qizi, J. Z. R. (2024). УЗБЕКИСТОН ХУДУДЛАРИДА ҚИШЛОҚ ХУЖАЛИГИ МАҲСУЛОТЛАРИНИ ИШЛАБ ЧИҚАРИШ САМАРОДОРЛИГИ ТАҲЛИЛИ. *Science and innovation*, 3(Special Issue 24), 616-621.
 9. Tajenova, G. E., Baijanov, S. X., Abishov, M. S., & Madreimov, A. K. (2022). PROVIDING AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTS TO THE POPULATION AND FINANCING IT BY THE STATE WAYS TO IMPROVE SUPPORT. *NeuroQuantology*, 20(22), 1598.
 10. Utegenova, S., & Mirzabaeva, U. (2024). TODAY'S IMPORTANCE AND PROSPECTS OF AUDIT ACTIVITIES IN UZBEKISTAN. *Евразийский журнал академических исследований*, 4(6), 93-95.

11. Utegenova, S., & Rozumova, D. (2024). DIRECTIONS FOR IMPROVING TAX AUDIT. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(6).
12. Utegenova, S., & Oralbaeva, F. (2024). O'zbekiston iqtisodiyotiga xorijiy investitsiyalar oqimini oshirishda mamlakatning investitsion muhiti jozibadorligini oshirish. *Журнал академических исследований нового Узбекистана*, 1(6), 131-134.
13. Сарсеновна, Ш. Д. (2023). ВЫБОР УПРАВЛЕНЧЕСКИХ РЕШЕНИЙ ПО МОМЕНТУ ДОСТИЖЕНИЯ МАКСИМАЛЬНОЙ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ПРОИЗВОДСТВА ХЛОПКА-СЫРЦА.
14. Шамшетова, Д. С. (2023). ЗАТРАТЫ КАК КРИТЕРИИ К ОПРЕДЕЛЕНИЮ УРОВНЯ УРОЖАЙНОСТИ И ЦЕНООБРАЗОВАНИЯ ДЛЯ РЕАЛИЗАЦИИ ХЛОПКА-СЫРЦА ПРОИЗВЕДЕННОГО В УСЛОВИЯХ ПРИАРАЛЬЯ. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 34, 319-324.
15. Tulenova, K., Ubaydullayeva, S., Gaziyeva, R., Mamayusupov, U., Mamadjonova, M., & Turdikulova, E. (2024, June). The Introduction of Information Technologies Into Educational and Laboratory Complexes is an Important Step Towards the Digitalization of Uzbekistan. In *2024 4th International Conference on Technology Enhanced Learning in Higher Education (TELE)* (pp. 48-53). IEEE.
16. Qurbonazarovna, M. M. (2024). OZBEKISTON TARAQQIYOTINING YANGI DAVRIDA TALIM SIFATINI OSHIRISHNING SINERGETIK IMKONIYATLARI. *Science and innovation*, 3(Special Issue 18), 65-67.
17. Turabekova, S., & Ibadova, N. (2024, April). Different Ways Of Improving Listening Skill In Learning Foreign Languages. In *Conference Proceedings: Fostering Your Research Spirit* (pp. 236-238).
18. Ibadova, N. (2024, April). Nutqdagi Ekspressivlikning Leksik Tasnifi. In *Conference Proceedings: Fostering Your Research Spirit* (pp. 319-323).

19. Axmatilloevna, I. N. (2024). Specific Characteristics Of Text Category. *Open Access Repository*, 10(3), 131-136.
20. Qurbanazarovna, M. M. (2023). PRELIMINARY IDEAS OF NECESSITY AND ACCIDENT. *World Bulletin of Social Sciences*, 26, 44-46.